

The Role of Female Leadership to Create Competitive Advantage

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Abstract— This study aims to evaluate the role of women leadership for creating competitive advantage in Higher Education Institutions – HEIs - in Brazilian Northeastern region. As specific goals it aims to describe the characteristics of the women managers of the HEIs studied, identify the leadership style adopted by women managers of the researched institutions and further highlight points that are considered important for women leaders as a competitive advantage. The research is characterized as qualitative, documental and descriptive. Content analysis was used to analyze data. The results showed that women leaders exhibit the following characteristics: appreciation for relationships; results-oriented, agility, perseverance, teamwork, creativity and planning, adopt a participative leadership style; highlight the ability of the staff to create and develop actions turned to the quality of the service and qualification of the professionals involved and efficiency and quality to attend customers and their needs. The surveyed leaders took actions aiming competitive advantage using intuition and also analyzing company and market conditions.

Keywords-Women, Labor market, Behavior, Leadership, Competitive Advantage.

I. INTRODUCTION

The women universe has been undergoing through transformations in social, professional and economic areas, this emphasized the need to know the new feminine characteristics. Among Companies where women have been working, Higher Education Institutions – HEIs - stand up, because this market is expanding. There was an increase in the number of colleges in recent decades, which generated savings and increased the number of educational services offered.

In this study, to point out the women leadership characteristics, it was used the work of [1], to study the leadership style it was used [2] and [3]. Regarding to competitive advantage, [4] [5] [6] were referred.

It was not found, in general literature, studies aiming to analyze the role of the female leadership for creating competitive advantage in HEIs in the northeast of Brazil. Given this, the following research question came up: What is the role of female leadership for creating competitive advantage in the Brazilian Northeastern region? Thus, the present study aims to evaluate the role of the female leadership for creating competitive advantage in HEIs in the Brazilian northeast. And in a more specific way, it seeks to describe the characteristics of the female leadership; identify which leadership style was adopted by women managers and highlights points that are considered important to create competitive advantage by these leaders.

II. CLASSICAL APPROACHES TO LEADERSHIP

Lewin (1973) [7] defines leadership as "decisive determinant of group atmosphere. In almost all cases, a good conflict resolution requires the activity of prepared and

democratic leaders"; [8] defines leadership as a process of helping to change certain essential aspects for seizing the changing conditions of the economy and the market. As for [9] leadership is a process in which the individual influences others to commit themselves to the pursuit of common goals, establishing a personal interaction that may be perceived as a managerial function. According to [10] leadership is developed in a specific context of interactions, combining the variables of the role to be played with the motivations, resources and attributes of leaders and expectations, resources, aspirations and attitudes of their followers.

A. Theory of Traits

In this approach, specific characteristics that a leader should have are taken into account. According to [11] the approach of traits of leadership states that a good leader is born complete. Thus, [9] says that leadership based only on traits doesn't explain sufficiently the concept and arguments that characteristics, at most, only increase the probability of someone to be an effective leader.

According to Dubrin (1998) [12], the characteristics of a leader, his personality traits alone, will not make a difference, for acquiring an effective leadership, it is necessary that him or her possess others fundamental behaviors and skills.

Thus, many scholars in the field of Management have concluded that it takes much more than just being born with leadership traits, leaders are not born complete, but are constructed with a lot of investment in training so the individual can become an effective leader.

B. Theories of Behavior

The theory of leadership states that people can be prepared to take a leadership role. For that it is needed to study and build the forms of exercising power, supported on the basic beliefs about man and human nature [13] but for [9] there are three types of management style: autocratic: refers to the leader as the only responsible for determining the steps in implementing the goals as well as setting guidelines; democratic or consultative: presents an interaction with the workgroup, seeking definitions through participation and interaction; Liberal: it is characterized by the total absence of discussions with the groups, leaving the entire responsibility on their behalf.

According to Limongi-Franca and Arellano (2002) [13] the theory of leadership states that people can be prepared to take a leadership role. For that it is needed to study and build the forms of exercise of power, supported on the basic beliefs about man and human nature. For White and Lippitt (1975) apud Dazzi (2002) [14], there are three types of management style:

a) *The autocratic: refers to the leader as the only responsible for determining the steps in implementing the goals as well as setting guidelines;*

b) *The democratic or consultative: presents an interaction with the workgroup, seeking definitions through participation and interaction;*

c) *Liberal: it is characterized by the total absence of discussions with the group, leaving the entire responsibility on their behalf.*

The leadership styles cited by [2] are going to be used in this work as the basis, when it comes to types of leadership used. This author states that leadership style can present itself in three ways: autocratic, participative and the total freedom type.

The autocratic leaders hold the most part of the authority to them, perform decisions with confidence and take for granted that the followers are going to be able to accomplish them. There is no concern on the part of the leader in the attitudes that his followers take after his decisions.

The second type is the participative style of leadership: the leader shares his decisions with other members. There are three types of participative leaders: consultative (consults his subordinates before making a decision, however they retain for themselves the final authority) consensual (instigates the debate in groups and then make a decision that reflects the consensus of the group) and democratic (provide the ultimate authority to the group, having a role of a "bridge" to collect opinions and make an election before taking a decision).

The third and last type is the leadership style of total freedom: the group receives all the authority and control. The tasks are presented to the group that has unconditional freedom to act in the search of achieving results; the leader participates only if requested by the group.

The behavior that leaders use to establish some influence on his subordinates to do their jobs, aiming to reach the established goals reflects the leadership styles adopted by them. Thus several studies have been developed involving leadership style, they still don't cover the situational issues such as the approach on the relationships among leaders, followers and context.

C. Contingency Theory of Leadership

The aspects surrounding the process of leadership are highlighted while focusing on the different styles of the leader's behavior. According to [14] the successful leader is the one who knows and is aware of the internal forces that affect behavior, including the individuals with whom he has a connection, the characteristics of the organization and its environment. Reinforcing this statement [13] say that leadership depends on the set composed by the leader, followers and situation, emphasizing the behavioral characteristics of those being led, the situation and the intended objectives during the process as a whole. Meanwhile, [16] shows that seeking balance is the best way to work the environmental influences and the personality of the person in the role of leader, in other words, both the historical forces create situations in which the leaders emerge and its particular characteristics help them to assume and hold their position as leaders. Thus, to ensure effectiveness in the leadership, says the author, it is necessary to combine the environment and the appropriate skills to lead according to the context.

III. EMERGING THEORIES ON LEADERSHIP

D. Charismatic Leadership

The charismatic leader starts by declaring a fascinating insight to those being led, with the goal of providing a sense of community, thus linking the present with the expectation of a hopeful future for the organization and those being led. The leader communicates high expectations and demonstrates confidence that followers will accomplish it. With this behavior manages to raise self-esteem, self-confidence, and demonstrates courage and conviction to accomplish all goals [13]. Charismatic leaders show strong proximity with the goals and objectives that they intend to accomplish and have a personal commitment to these goals. This type of leader is seen as assertive, unconventional and self-confident, are the true agents of changes and do not allow the maintenance of the status quo [17].

E. Visionary Leadership

Visionary leadership is the ability to create and articulate a realistic view that makes the present better. This view is properly selected and implemented bringing skills, talents and resources together to make it happen [17].

The visionary leaders seek high-risk positions; have a peculiar way of relating to people in an intuitive and comprehensive way. They usually share their ideas, and do not depend on the organization to have a vision or a perception of the environment. These leaders face the future and worry about taking risks. However if such leaders are not in line with the managerial leaders, they can fail because they run more risks. So it is necessary to differentiate leaders from managers, since the former may emerge or may be appointed by the group, and

the second is named with legitimate powers to reward or punish his subordinates based on the formal authority along with their followers [3].

F. Transformational Leadership

The Transformational Leadership Theory focuses on the development process of those being led. Leaders acquire responsibility of reshaping organizational practices, aiming their adaptation to environmental changes. According to this author, the notion of this transformative leadership is critical for shaping the future of organizations and of those being led [18].

The Transformational Leadership Theory focuses on the development process of those being led. The expression transformational, according to [18], refers to the responsibility leaders have to reshape organizational practices, aiming their adaptation to environmental changes. According to this author, the notion of this transformative leadership is critical for shaping the future of organizations and of those being led.

Limongi-Franca and Arellano (2002) [13] state that it is of great importance to recognize the feminine style of leadership as natural potential for entrepreneurial organizations, as in this type of organization it is easier to absorb the kind of style, promote more incentives to women to act, considering that this type of organization strives for innovation among other characteristics inherent to the environment and culture developed.

G. Women's Leadership

To associate the practice of leadership to the female actions it is necessary to point out what [19] said when analyzing the access of women to a Company, that it is away from the stigmas of the traditional functions of secretarial and worker, leading us to understand the differences that involve men and women regarding to the production in the world of organizations, such redefinition of roles leads to question the most fundamental role that has existed since the beginning of mankind, the gender distinction in social organizations.

Thus, the contemporary women have been increasing their participation in the labor market, they are now required to be successful in their professional activities, and thus, end up creating a model, "her own way" to manage and act in organizations. According to [20], there is a distinction between feminine and masculine characteristics, "the woman does not reveal herself as safe as the man in the organization, since man imposes himself and takes a risk to make the others believe in his competence, the woman in business and in administration is scrupulous and complete".

The increasing number of women in management positions allows showing the difference between men and women in regard to professional practices and not only in terms of a single dimension, the occupations. After all, the set of qualities needed by executives in their roles vary according to the culture of a Company [19].

In studies based on post-structuralism, authors such as [21] and [22] characterize the femininity in management as well as the management model that values the collaborative and relational behavior, forming a model of "post-heroic

leadership" antagonistic to the model of "heroic leadership" that was individualistic, focused on a few leaders and in an authoritarian system of power. Thus [21] distinguishes some traits to define two models of leadership: the female of the post-heroic leadership and male of the heroic leadership. Therefore:

Men and women can show them, but traits as individualism, control, assertiveness and abilities to advocate are socially assigned to men and generally perceived as male. In contrast, the traits associated to the new post-heroic leadership are female. Again men or women can present them, but traits as empathy, communication, vulnerability and ability to conquer and collaboration are socially assigned to women and perceived as feminine [21].

Characteristics as encouraging, participation, sharing power and information, stimulate values and motivate others at their work environment and also features like flexibility, sensitivity, prudence and caution are female characteristics cited by [23]; [24] adds that women present characteristics that are natural to them, such as appreciation of teamwork, perseverance, constancy; little immediacy; reasoning ability in the long term, are more adaptive, flexible and open to continuous learning.

Regarding to the Brazilian context, there has been studies carried out by the Caliper Brazil in partnership with HSM Brazil, which aimed to know the profile of Brazilian executives. This study involved sixty-six interviews with women who occupied positions of president, vice president and director of various Companies from various parts of the country and in different sectors of the economy. The results of this study showed that women recognize that there are differences in female and male styles, first because women would be more focused on the collective well-being than men and second that women take more decisions based on intuition than men.

IV. COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE AND GENDER

Organizations, in general, seek to conquer a sustainable long-term performance; to understand this phenomenon; studies have identified three variables: structure of the Company, competitive environment and competitive strategies. A company will only have competitive advantage when it is using a strategy to create value that is not being used by another. Therefore, the company is maintaining the sustainability of its advantage, given that its competitors cannot duplicate its strategy [4], but according to [24], in order to get competitiveness, a company must always seek to meet the needs of the clients, as doing that the company is able to remain in the market longer. Competitive advantage is, according to [25] directly related to the external environment, the internal environment and behavior, attitude of senior management, and other variables such as:

a) *Environmental factors - are considered as the coefficient of the strength of the competitors, the availability of human, financial and material resources, the degree to access more advanced technology and ultimately the institutional image of the company;*

b) *Factors related to the general situation of the Company - refers to the cost reduction and simplification of procedures resulting from the incorporated technology, financial stability, the management information system, the good image of products and services, among others.*

c) *Factors inherent to the position of senior management - are interlinked to the acceptance of risks, the effect of exploiting the opportunities, the existence of well-defined objectives, strategies that could be operationalized and policies, in addition to the market-oriented vision, leadership ability and motivation, innovation and creativity. Highlighting that the resources must be well managed and that appropriate controls are maintained.*

Porter (1989) [6] defines competitiveness as "the search for a favorable competitive position in an industry, the fundamental arena in which competition occurs". The author says that competition can be evaluated from the perspective of five competitive forces:

d) *Suppliers: They can be a threat for its lack, delaying in delivery or the lack of quality in the products offered.*

e) *Buyers: companies seek to understand and meet the needs of its customer. The buyer's power influences the price that companies can charge and also the cost and investments.*

f) *Substitutes: are products that have similar or equivalent function developed by competitors, resulting in loss of customers.*

g) *Potential entrants: Free competition means that market is open to companies.*

h) *Rivalry among competitors: rivalry faced by companies may take different levels ranging from rigid to aggressive and even unethical, making it imperative for companies to anticipate to their competitors to stay in the market.*

Using such forces, the company can achieve competitive advantage that comes from the value that the organization can present to its consumers that outweigh the costs of production of the company. Thus, a strategy for the company would be the ability to keep in a position of superiority in the competition [6]; the actions of leaders may cause a disproportional impact on the structure of businesses, due to its size and influence on buyers, suppliers and other competitors. At the same time, large portions of market leaders ensure that everything that changes the overall industrial structure will affect them too. A leader must constantly match its own competitive position to the best state of the industry as a whole [6]. According to [26] in colleges, the search for competitive advantage is not different from other sectors of the market, but some of these companies are not aware of its potential and of the value to show to their customers (students and parents), this is a risk factor for achieving their organizational strategies and their positioning in the market.

As to the role of leaders and the five forces to developing competitive advantage, [6] states that "the actions of leaders may cause a disproportional impact on the structure of businesses, due to its size and its influence on buyers, suppliers and other competitors. At the same time, large portions of market leaders ensure that everything that changes the overall industrial structure will affect them too. A leader must constantly match its own competitive position to the best state of the industry as a whole".

Porter (1989) [6] developed a typology that involves three generic strategies, that can be applied to companies and provide them competitive advantage:

a) *Cost leadership: The Company has a wide competitive target, reaching various segments, seeking position in the market by offering products and services at low cost, without neglecting quality. This provides a barrier against rivalry of the competitors.*

b) *Differentiation: It can refer to a product or service, but the ideal situation is to be unique in the business sector and seen like that. The company has a wide competitive purpose and can serve many segments. There is one or more attributes that many consumers consider important and then, firms choose one or more of these characteristics and position themselves to meet the needs of its customers.*

c) *Focus: The Company selects a segment or group of segments in the industry and adapts its strategies to meet their needs, refusing the other segments. This strategy has two variants: the focus on costs and focus on differentiation. Focus on cost means that the company seeks to achieve a cost advantage in the segment that was chosen. Focus on differentiation demands that the company must find a differentiation, apply it to its products and then present it to the segment that was chosen.*

According to Porter (1989) [6], it is possible that an organization uses all the generic competitive strategies and ends up achieving not only one of them, but a mix of strategies; this is what the author calls the "middle ground" strategy. This strategy leads to a lower performance, given that a company of "middle ground" will compete with companies that are leaders using cost or differentiation focus and are better prepared to compete in these segments. Organizational leaders are the ones that will fit the generic strategies of their companies, because the leader is responsible for setting the direction to be followed and the vision of the future to be achieved in order to disseminate and inspire his team to overcome obstacles.

A. *Competitive Advantage and Women's Leadership*

Market is undergoing through rapid and constant changes, it means that companies operate in a competitive scenario, which, according to [27], make organizations to value their leaders, so that they can build a favorable relationship with their team and are able to reach the desired future for the organization, [28] argue that these rapid changes in the current scenario, especially since the 1990s, have been helping companies to realize the necessity to modify their working

methods, their management models and to invest in leaders to make them stronger and able to work in any scenario.

The widely accepted view that social scientists expert on leadership have that women and men lead in the same way should be very substantially revised. Similarly, the view, proclaimed in some popular books on management, that female and male leaders have distinctive, gender-stereotypic styles also requires revision. The masculine way of management is characterized by competitiveness, hierarchical authority, high control for the leader, and unemotional and analytic problem solving. The author also argues that women prefer and tend to behave in terms of an alternative feminine leadership model characterized by cooperativeness, collaboration, lower control, and problem solving based on intuition and empathy as well as rationality [29].

To highlight the importance of leadership and specifically the female leadership in organizations as a distinguishing and participative factor in the labor market, there have been studies in national and international levels. As an example, it could be cited [28], in his thesis, entitled "Portals in the Glass Ceiling: the role of Knowledge in the surreptitious leadership advancement of women with high potential for management", in which he describes the importance of female leadership that permeates society. The author suggests throughout his work that the female leadership emerges as a potential resource in companies and should be more explored nowadays.

Another international study that should be referred is the one developed by [30], entitled "Organizational Commitment: the glass ceiling and New England higher education executive position." This study deals with the relationship between organizational commitment of educational institutions and the rise of women's career in New England. The proposed objective in this study was to verify the existence of invisible barriers at work for women. To reach this goal, women in positions of president, vice president, chancellors and executive officers of the New England region were researched. This result of this study shows two conclusions: the first refers to the existence of the so-called "glass ceiling" and the second that women in the region are encouraged to occupy senior positions in higher education. Thus, the author considered that gender is a facilitator to achieve high positions in the educational sector.

In these competitive times, organizations need more resources and capabilities to reach competitive advantage. In this context, employees become increasingly significant source of competitive advantage; human resources as the focus of companies indicates that managers are seeking new ways to rethink the business concept and trying to work towards critical success factors for the firm [32] [33].

Labor market has been going through changes due to technology and the digital age, it has also given a new image to women leaders. "Women now have many different role models for leadership – they don't need to feel they must copy the old male "command and control" style that flattens so many hopes and kills creativity. But sadly, there are still many men in powerful positions who hold the deeply-ingrained philosophical view that women are biologically ill-equipped for leadership in business. Thank goodness these dinosaurs are slowly being overtaken by many outstanding male leaders who

recognize and reward the enormous contribution women make" [31].

B. Critical Factors for Success

The search and the efforts organizations make to enter and to keep in a market will depend on the behavior and attitudes of managers to achieve their goals. A positive result in this area implies competitiveness for organizations. Critical factors for success can lead to satisfactory results contributing to a good competitive performance for individuals, departments and organizations and they are related to the particular situation of each manager [35]. The main method to identify the critical factors is to interview managers; external information such as data on the structure of the market and the customers' perception trends are essential. Many factors also require the coordination of groups of data scattered throughout the organization [35].

The critical factors for success can be called competitive factors, once they can be used to detect the need of customers; consequently providing information to identify what is important to them, such as price, quality, staff capacity, reliable delivery, innovative products and services, wide range of products and services and possibility to change quantity or time to deliver product or service. The variables that form critical factors for success are highly relevant to understand facts directly related to leadership [36].

V. METHODOLOGY

As for goals, this research is descriptive; [37] states that, for a descriptive research, "the key focus of the studies lies in the desire to know the community, its traits, agents and problems"; [38] complements this definition stating that a qualitative research "works with the universe of meanings, motives, aspirations, beliefs, values and attitudes."

As to the research design, documental research and multi case study were used. Considering the approach of [38], the case study is a way of doing research, investigating a phenomenon within a real life context, when the boundaries are not clearly determined in order to promote the use of multiple sources of evidence.

Regarding the documentary research, [39] states that this resembles the literature research, differing only in the nature of the sources, as the last one uses the contribution of multiple authors on a particular subject; while the first uses materials that haven't yet received analytical treatment or still can be redesigned according to the survey results and internal rules developed by institutions.

The object of this research is women working as executives, general coordination and strategic positions. Fifteen women were researched. For data collection, it was used a semi-structured interview, applied directly to the subjects of the research. The research was held between December, 2012 and February, 2013. According to [37], Semi-structured interview, in general, is the one that goes from certain basic questions, supported by theories and hypotheses that matter to the research and then offers wide fields of questions, result of new

TABLE I. ORIGINS OF THE SAMPLE USED.

CITY	SAMPLE	PRIVATE	PUBLIC	INTERIEWS(E)
Terezina	15	15	-	E1 to E15
Fortaleza	4	4	-	E16 to E19
Natal	6	5	1	E20 to E25
Recife	8	6	2	E26 to E33
TOTAL	33	30	3	

Source: Data of the research (2013; 2014).

hypotheses that arise as the responses of the informant are received.

A. Sample

The region researched is composed by nine States; it was chosen, by convenience, four of its capitals to get the data to be used in this work. The first city is Terezina, in Piauí State, the second is Fortaleza, in Ceará State, the third is Natal, in Rio Grande do Norte State and the fourth is Recife, in Pernambuco State. These are the most populous cities in the region. Table 1 indicates the cities and the respective origin of the sample used (city, type of university).

The content analysis used as a technique for data analysis is conceptualized by [40] as a set of the contents of the messages, drivers (quantitative or not) that allow the inference of knowledge concerning the conditions of production / reception (inferred variables) of these messages. The content studied was divided in categories, forming organized and easy to understand blocks. Two categories were formed: Profile of female leadership and competitive advantage, the first was divided in two subcategories: female leadership characteristics and leadership style; the second category was also subdivided: critical points of success and actions developed to achieve competitive advantage.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This analysis is presented for the purpose of answering the objectives proposed in this study, so this item is divided in four parts: a) characteristics of the female leadership; b) leadership style; c) critical success points; d) competitive advantage. Data from public universities, once they were only three, will be analyzed right after it is done to the data obtained in private ones.

The profile of the female manager, characterized by the features as extremely important by them, reveals that they value and highlight: the value of relationship, balance, agility, results-oriented, perseverance, teamwork, creativity and planning. Therefore, it was observed that such characteristics respond to the specific objective, which is to describe the characteristics of the female leadership of the managers of the private HEIs studied. Two of the leaders from public universities highlighted the necessity of being fond of keeping up to date and making researches. This result is in accordance to [11] that states in regard to practical issues such as decision making the leader can engage himself in planning toward strategic outcomes, [23] emphasize the characteristic of appreciation and encouragement of the relationship; emphasizing that women become important for the company

by softening the relations and make use of a sensitive and empathetic behavior while [24] highlights the perseverance as a characteristic that women value in the organizational universe. These characteristics were also reported by the interviewed women in a survey conducted by [1].

Regarding the leadership style adopted by women leaders, it should be noted that the participative style was predominant in the interviews, which shows that these women have a strong tendency to share decision making with their employees. The three leaders from public universities referred that they usually take decision consulting people around and one of them said this procedure is also common for men leaders. This responds to the goal that aimed to identify the leadership style adopted by women managers of the institutions studied. This result corroborates the one achieved by [9] that identified the participative style when researching the female managers at the Paraíba State University in Brazil. It should be noted that Paraíba State is also in the Brazilian Northeastern region (between Pernambuco and Rio Grande do Norte States).

Regarding the decisive points for success, the respondents believe that high quality, staff capacity, meeting the costumers need, innovative products and services are critical points in order to the Company obtain credibility and acceptance, as well as to add value to its products and customers. Two leaders from Recife and one from Natal added that improving the chance to access labor market should be also considered. The leaders from public universities did not have different opinions. This is in tune with [41], when he says that one of the ways to the success of a company is to understand clearly who it is, its ability and business and what values are created for the customers, doing so, the company maintains its customers and reach new others.

As to competitive advantage, 12 out of the 33 participants (two from public universities), informed that developed actions focused on service quality and qualification, pedagogical practices, promotion of good quality and efficient service to customers and its needs; [42] agrees with this finding when states that the excellence of customer service is also a powerful competitive advantage. The service adds value through personal relationship and support offered to the customer.

According to Band, (1997) [43], competitive advantage is directly related to the external environment, the internal environment and behavior and attitude of top managers; these are typical actions that will generate competitive advantage [25]. It was observed that 15 out of 33 interviewees pointed out situations not related to strategy or internal or external environment as actions to create competitive advantage, among them one is from a public university. The results are shown on Table 2.

VII. CLOSING REMARKS

The objective of this work was to evaluate the role of the female leadership for creating competitive advantage in HEIs in the Brazilian northeast region.

In response to the question posed in the survey, it can be said that the leaders have the following characteristics: the appreciation of the relationship, balance, agility, results-oriented, perseverance, teamwork, creativity and planning,

TABLE II. ACTIONS FOR CREATING COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

Interviews (E)	Answers about actions to develop competitive advantages	Actions to create competitive advantage / number of interviews
E2, E3, E5, E7, E11, E13, E14, E18, E26, E27**, E28, E29, E30, E22*, E32.	Didn't present actions to create competitive advantage	15 / 33 → 45 %
E10, E24, E23	Didn't answer this item	3 / 33 → 9,5 %
E9, E20, E33	Response oriented to the skills	3 / 33 → 9,5 %
E1; E4; E6; E8, E12, E15, E16, E17, E19, E21, E25, E31**	Developed actions focused on creation of competitive advantage	12 / 33 → 36 %
* Leader from public university (Natal).		
** Leaders from public universities (Recife).		
Total		33

Source: Data of the research (2013; 2014)

adopt a leadership participative style, highlight the staff qualification as the most important point to apply actions turned to competitive advantage followed by high quality, are always searching for innovative products and services or to implement actions aiming better quality, pedagogical practices are up to date and seek better services to customers to meet their needs.

It can be also concluded that women leaders of the researched HEIs in the Brazilian Northeastern region take competitive actions using intuition as well as analyzing internal and external conditions of the company. This result indicates that female leaders have an advantage to create competitive actions once they consider one more dimension, intuition. This indicates that, in the region researched, females leaders are conducting their organizations to competitive advantage through a way that was not pointed out yet, combining and taking the best from theoretical and empirical resources.

It was not intention to establish a difference among leaders from public and private universities and it should be noticed that the sample from public universities was not significant and did not show significant differences from the sample from private universities. A future study analyzing specifically the differences among female leaders in public and private universities may bring to light issues that may reflect the differences among these organizations. This is highlighted because two of the three interviewed leaders from different public universities emphasized the necessity of being fond of keeping up to date and making researches as an important characteristic in the profile of a female leader; this was not referred by the ones from private universities and might represent an important difference among the objectives of the universities.

As it was stressed above, it was not intention to establish differences among universities but it was not found female leaders in public universities in Fortaleza and Terezina and, in the others cities it was found a big difference between the number of female leaders in public and private universities.

This could be another difference among these universities that deserves to be scientifically analyzed.

Although the study was multicase, it would be interesting to broaden the scope of the research in order to cover a greater number and types of organizations and involve aspects such as the performance of organizations allied to the creation of competitive advantage, as well as organizations in other states, regions or countries.

This study contributes to organizations that may need information about how female managers position themselves in the process of developing and applying competitive advantage. It also may be useful to organizations that seek to combine the characteristics of woman leadership and the leadership style adopted to promote harmony and more fruitful relationships during the process to develop competitive actions.

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